

A fork in the road of change: A comparison of simple and complex organizational change models

Aeron Zentner

Change has become a vital element in the fabric of organizations to establish and maintain in the competitive global market. Many theories and models across leadership and management literature have emerged to facilitate and drive changes. Though many of these models have been considered to be highly effective in certain settings. Through the review of literature, there has been limited work comprising the different aspects of change models to best fit situations. The focus of the study was to determine the strengths and weaknesses of two change models support leader decisions to identify application opportunities for change model fit.

Keywords—Change Management, Leadership, Strategy

I. INTRODUCTION

The emerging global economy has required firms to be adaptable and flexible to meet demands to gain and/or maintain competitive advantage and secure stability in a volatile business market. Beer and Nohria (2000) indicated that in order to thrive in the new global economy, organizations must continue to strength organizational culture and advance shareholder value within the midst of integrating effective change. The review of literature has found a wealth of change strategies and models that use simplistic to complex approaches to drive change. However, there is an apparent needs to compare depth of complexity to strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats to leadership, change resistance and communication processes. The following paper will discuss and assess the McKinsey 7-S and Lewin's Change Management Models to determine the implication of leaders must take into account when selecting a change model to employ.

II. MCKINSEY 7-S MODEL

The McKinsey 7-S Model taken an interwoven approach to change which incorporates seven factors which are categorized in two categories of hard and soft elements. The hard elements are defined as easy to identify and manage, while soft elements consist of hard to qualify factors which carry high influence on organizational behavior. The hard element category includes strategy (i.e. a plan created to achievement and/or maintain competitive advantage), structure (i.e. the organizational arrangement and the hierarchal representation of the organization), and systems (i.e. the operational procedures and activities). The soft element category includes skills (i.e. the knowledge, skills, and capabilities of human capital), style (i.e. diversity of employees recruited and continuously trained), and shared values (i.e. the norms and standards of behavioral expectation of the organization) (Jurevicius, 2013). The

utilization of the model helps leaders postulate effect of potential changes prior to implementation.

The implementation strategy of this model indicates leaders must assess the seven different factors to define gaps and opportunities which can cross-pollinate to strengthen the other factors within the model. Singh (2013) indicates that a key component to this model is built around transparency and communication. Therefore as organization develop a framework for change, it is essential to maintain clarity, openness and integrity in communication efforts regarding change. This strategy can help garner trust and attract organizational participation and adoption to change. Though the model can be highly complex, it provides a compressive roadmap to introduce, implement and integrate change with highly anticipated outcomes.

III. LEWIN'S CHANGE MANAGEMENT MODEL

The Lewin's Change Management Models follows a three-step strategy to which focuses on the transitional decision of change completed at the individual level. Lewin (1958) found that individuals prefer to shift based on certainty and security. According to Lewin (1951), change happens within three steps which include unfreezing, change and refreezing. The first step of the model labeled unfreeze focuses employee preparation to change. Within this step the employee can be engaged with an internal or external environmental assessment, which builds credibility to warrant movement from the current state. Literature supports this strategy with a focus on evidence based decision making and effective mode to jumpstart change (Pfeffer & Sutton, 2006; Trank, 2015). The second step within the process is outlined as change or transition. This step includes the initiation, implementation and execution of the change strategy. This instance can be volatile as unexpected outcomes can occur and requires effective responsiveness to maintain momentum through the transition. The third step labeled as refreeze is the phase which the change has been fully implemented and the stability is reestablished.

Lewis (2012) suggests that this model allows for broad application and in certain instances can be used as an inception of to change. The implications to change leadership behavior focuses on each step specifically step one with the provision of the need for change supported with evidence. Lewin (1948) suggested utilizing as force field analysis by indicating that "An issue is held in balance by the interaction of two opposing sets of forces - those seeking to promote change (driving forces) and those attempting to maintain the status quo (restraining forces)." This tool provides a visional comparison of determining the

factors or forces that need to change and the barriers for the change to occur. Additionally, leaders need to draw attention to the execution of change strategies and to continuously ensure that communication challenges are clear in presenting progression status updates, providing feedback and support to issues that may arise through the transition. The empirical work of Rosemond and Asamoah-Appiah (2012) supports this perspective that employee acceptance in only one portion of the change process and requires management to build trust through actions and communication to hinder resistance to change.

IV. METHOD AND FINDINGS

Based on the review of literature, strengths, weakness, opportunities and threats (SWOT) analyses were conducted on both change models to best present implication on leadership strategies in determine which model best suits the change need. This analysis was conducted based on the observation of the change model components and strategies coupled with the review of literature.

Table 1 *S.W.O.T. Analysis of McKinsey 7s Model*

Strengths	Weaknesses
The model allows for an effective strategy to identify and understand the complexities of an organization	Due to the interwoven structure of the model, if one aspect changes each aspect is affected
The model provides direction for change	The model carries a high level of complexity which may be challenging to integrate and manage
The model combines logical and emotional factors	
Opportunities	Threats
The assessment of the factors must be uniform, thus limiting the aspect of over or under analyzing factors	The model may not be able to maintain relevance with shifting global market, as changes modify the entire structure and may cause confusion
The integration of the model creates a cohesive culture and structure within the organization	Poor communication can limit interaction, leading to poor feedback and poor understanding and clarity regarding the change strategy

The findings in Table 1 suggest that leaders need to draw attention to the external climate and the complexity of the change strategy with associated outcomes. Due to the comprehensiveness of the implementation, it is essential for leaders to determine the impact and longevity of the change strategy as major post-implementation shifts based on market

could be detrimental to the organizational culture. Additionally, leaders must foster a strong communication network that indicates impact of behaviors and implications related to modifications in the strategy. By drawing consideration to these matters, leaders can effectively assess modify and execute changes across the spectrum of the 7-S framework to effectively drive change.

Table 2 *S.W.O.T. Analysis of Lewin's Change Management Model*

Strengths	Weaknesses
Simplistic in nature, as it does not require many steps	Does not provide direction to leadership
The approach is flexible and broad and can be applied to a range of situations	Does not specify prerequisites to the unfreeze or change periods (strong communication structure, collaborative environment, access to data)
Utilizes and employee focus to create a cultural shift through global buy-in	
Opportunities	Threats
Global understanding of the internal climate internal and externally	Disgruntled employees that are resistant to change
Innovation through internal and external assessment driving change	Poor culture that is not collaborative which will yield poor interaction and limit buy-in
Can spark engagement as it requires employee interaction, feedback and participation	Poor communication can limit interaction, leading to poor feedback and weak clarity on change progression
	Refreeze periods may be limited which is due to the volatile business market which requires agility to change

The findings in Table 2 suggest that prior to model implementation that it is imperative that leaders have a true understanding of the organizational climate and operational functions. By addressing these issues, leaders can create a foundation for successful implementation through the timely provision of information (e.g. evidence, data) to spark interest and evoke need, trust in collaboration to develop and implement effective changes strategies, clear and concise communication channels to keep constituents abreast of progress and/or challenges and follow-up and assessment post-implementation. By addressing these aspects of the organizational environment, leaders can best position strategies for action in driving change.

V. LIMITATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

The review of the change models brought to fruition emerging opportunities and limitations to employing these models to facilitate change. Though this assessment provides a starting point for leaders to better determine model fit to achieve organizational directives or goals, however the assessment does not encompass all change models and strategies. Therefore, it would be recommended that further research needs to be conducted across more change models and strategies. This would add depth and breadth to the findings of the recent study.

VI. DISCUSSION

As the global economy continues to evolve, organizations are constantly required to adapt to changing market demands and change has become an inevitable response to maintain competitiveness (Biedenbacha & Soumllderholma, 2008). The review of literature has found many different models that employ simplistic to complex approaches to facilitate transition. Through the review of literature and the assessment of McKinsey 7-S and Lewin's Change Management Models one can posit that change falls within the parameter of setting, situation and depth. Through the SWOT analyses both models yielded positive and negative aspects, which would suggest that leaders should assess the organizational climate to determine which model to follow.

References

- [1] Beer, M., & Nohria, N. (2000). Cracking the code of change. *Harvard Business Review*, 78(3), 133-+.
- [2] Biedenbacha, T. and Soumllderholma, A. (2008). The challenge of organizing change in hypercompetitive industries: a literature review. *Journal of Change Management*, 8(2) 123-45.
- [3] Jurevicius, O. (2013). McKinsey 7s Model. *Strategic Management Insight*. Retrieved from <http://www.strategicmanagementinsight.com/tools/mckinsey-7s-model-framework.html>
- [4] Levasseur, R. E. (2001). People Skills: Change Management Tools: Lewin's Change Model. *Interfaces*, (4). 71.
- [5] Lewin, K. (1948). Resolving social conflicts: selected papers on group dynamics. New York: Harper and Brothers.
- [6] Lewin, K. (1951). *Field Theory in Social Science*. New York: Harper and Row.
- [7] Lewin, K. (1958) Group decision and social change in Readings in *Social Psychology*, eds. E. E. Maccoby, T. M. Newcomb, and E. L. Hartley, Holt, Rinehart and Winston, New York, pp. 197-211.
- [8] Lewis, A. (2012). Finding a model for managing change. *Training & Development (1839-8561)*, 39(5), 6-7.
- [9] Pfeffer, J., & Sutton, R. I. (2006). Evidence-based Management. *Harvard Business Review*, 84(1), 62-74.
- [10] Rosemond, B., & Asamoah Appiah, W. (2012). Resistance to Organisational Change: A Case Study of Oti Yeboah Complex Limited. *International Business and Management*, (1), 135.
- [11] Singh, A. (2013). A Study of Role of McKinsey's 7S Framework in Achieving Organizational Excellence. *Organization Development Journal*, 31(3), 39-50.
- [12] Trank, C. Q. (2015). "Reading" Evidence-Based Management: The Possibilities of Interpretation. *Academy Of Management Learning & Education*, 2015(1), 48-62. doi:10.5465/amle.2013.0444